

Graph-Based Insider Threat Detection from Authentication Logs using a Hybrid GATv2-LSTM-GAN Architecture

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Abstract. *Insider threats represent a major challenge for modern organizations, particularly in financial environments where malicious activities are often performed using legitimate credentials and therefore become difficult to distinguish from normal operational behavior. Traditional anomaly detection approaches commonly fail to capture the relational and temporal dependencies present in authentication logs, especially under severe class imbalance scenarios. This paper investigates insider threat detection through graph-based deep learning techniques and presents a hybrid **GATv2-LSTM-GAN** architecture designed to jointly model structural interactions, behavioral evolution, and rare anomalous events. The study is supported by a Systematic Literature Mapping (SLM) involving 22 primary studies, which identified the growing adoption of dynamic and heterogeneous graph representations, hybrid spatiotemporal architectures, and imbalance-aware learning strategies in cybersecurity research. Based on these findings, authentication logs were transformed into heterogeneous graphs representing employees, systems, devices, and interactions. The proposed architecture integrates GATv2 for relational representation learning, LSTM for temporal behavioral modeling, and GAN-based synthetic anomaly generation combined with Focal Loss to mitigate extreme imbalance. The experimental evaluation was conducted on a large-scale synthetic authentication dataset containing approximately 17.8 million events, where additional anomalous embeddings were generated through AnomalyGAN. Results demonstrate that the proposed hybrid architecture achieved robust performance under highly imbalanced conditions, outperforming the standalone Bi-LSTM baseline in terms of MCC and maintaining balanced Precision and Recall. Additionally, the study highlights the limitations of relying exclusively on ROC-AUC in rare-event cybersecurity scenarios and reinforces the importance of imbalance-aware evaluation metrics such as MCC and PR-AUC.*

1. Systematic Literature Mapping Study (SLM)

The search strategy was structured using the PICOC model (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcomes, and Context), which supported the identification of keywords and the construction of the search string [Kitchenham et al. 2009]. The search terms were iteratively refined to balance recall and precision, following recommendations for systematic mapping studies in software engineering [Petersen et al. 2015]. The automated search process was conducted across four major digital libraries widely used in cybersecurity and software engineering research: ACM Digital Library, IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, and Scopus.

The final search string adopted across the databases was: ("*insider threat*" OR "*insider anomaly*" OR "*malicious insider*" OR "*compromised account*" OR "*log anomaly*")

AND ("graph neural network" OR "GNN" OR "graph attention" OR "GATv2" OR "GCN") AND ("LSTM" OR "RNN" OR "recurrent" OR "GAN" OR "generative adversarial"). The searches were restricted to studies published between January 2018 and the search execution period. Some studies indexed as 2026 correspond to early-access publications already available online during the execution of the mapping process.

The inclusion and exclusion criteria adopted in the SLM are presented in Table 1.

Table 2 presents the quality assessment questions adopted in this study.

Table 1. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria of the SLM

Type	ID	Criterion Description
Inclusion	IC1	Articles written in English or Portuguese.
	IC2	Studies published between January 2018 and the present.
	IC3	Studies proposing or evaluating graph-based models applied to cybersecurity scenarios.
	IC4	Studies utilizing spatial (graph-based) and/or temporal modeling approaches.
Exclusion	EC1	Publications without peer review (e.g., grey literature).
	EC2	Studies not addressing insider threats, authentication anomalies, or log-based anomaly detection.
	EC3	Studies not using graph structures as the primary data representation.
	EC4	Studies exclusively based on traditional machine learning methods (e.g., RF, SVM).
	EC5	Abstracts, editorials, tutorials, posters, or studies lacking methodological description.
	EC6	Secondary studies such as systematic reviews and literature mappings.

Table 2. Quality Assessment Questions (QAQs)

ID	Assessment Question	Weight
QAQ1	Is the research objective and cybersecurity problem clearly defined?	1.0
QAQ2	Are the evaluation metrics adequate for imbalanced cybersecurity data?	1.0
QAQ3	Is the dataset described in terms of scale and origin?	1.0
QAQ4	Is there a clear strategy to address class imbalance?	1.0
QAQ5	Does the model explicitly address temporal dependencies?	1.0
QAQ6	Is the graph representation adequately detailed?	1.0

Table 3. Technical synthesis of the primary studies selected in the Systematic mapping, presenting architectures, temporal components, graph representations, data balancing strategies, application domains, datasets, and evaluation metrics (ordered by year).

ID	Citation	Base Architecture	Temporal Component	Graph Representation	Detection Level	Imbalance Handling	Synthetic Generation	User Journey	Application Domain	Datasets	Metrics
01	[Liu et al. 2019]	Heterogeneous GNN	None	Static, Heterogeneous	Node	None	No	Yes	Network, System, Others	Log2vec	Others
02	[Li et al. 2023]	GNN	None	Dynamic, Homogeneous	Node	Oversampling	Yes	No	System, Others	CERT r4.2	F1, Precision, Recall
03	[Yan et al. 2023]	GNN	Time-aware Att.	Dynamic, Heterogeneous	Edge	None	No	Yes	System	BGL; Thunderbird	Others, ROC
04	[Pal et al. 2023]	Others	LSTM	Static, Homogeneous	Node	Oversampling	No	Yes	Network, System	CERT r4.2	F1, Precision, Recall
05	[He et al. 2024]	GNN	None	Static, Homogeneous	Node	None	No	No	System	HDFS; BGL	F1, Precision, Recall
06	[Li et al. 2022]	GAT	None	Static, Homogeneous	Node	GAN	Yes	Yes	Network, System	CERT r4.2	F1, Precision, Recall
07	[Cai et al. 2024]	GATv2	None	Dynamic, Heterogeneous	Node	None	No	Yes	Network, System, Others	CERT r4.2; LANL	F1, ROC, Recall
08	[Wang et al. 2024]	Heterogeneous GNN	None	Static, Heterogeneous	Node	None	No	No	System, Others	BGL, HDFS, Thunderbird	F1, Precision, Recall
09	[Tang et al. 2024]	GNN	None	Static, Homogeneous	Node	None	No	No	System, Others	Forum, Halo, Novel	F1, PR-AUC, Precision, Recall
10	[Xu and Li 2024]	GCN	LSTM	Dynamic, Heterogeneous	Node	None	No	Yes	System	BGL, HDFS, Thunderbird	F1, PR-AUC, Precision, Recall
11	[Yumlembam et al. 2025]	GCN	LSTM	Dynamic, Heterogeneous	Node	Weighting	No	Yes	Network, System	CERT r4.2	F1, ROC, Recall
12	[Qi et al. 2025]	Heterogeneous GNN	Time-aware Att.	Dynamic, Heterogeneous	Node	Focal Loss	No	Yes	Network, System, Others	CERT r4.2; LANL	F1, Precision, Recall
13	[Liu et al. 2025c]	Heterogeneous GNN	None	Dynamic, Heterogeneous	Node	None	No	Yes	Network, System, Others	CERT r4.2	Others, ROC
14	[Tian et al. 2025]	GNN	None	Static, Heterogeneous	Node	Undersampling	No	Yes	Network, System	CERT r4.2; r6.2	F1, Precision, Recall
15	[Chu et al. 2025]	Heterogeneous GNN	Time-aware Att.	Dynamic, Heterogeneous	Node	Focal Loss	No	Yes	Network, System, Others	CERT r4.2; LANL	F1, ROC
16	[Yoon et al. 2025]	GAT	None	Dynamic, Heterogeneous	Graph	None	No	Yes	Network, System, Others	Provenance	F1, Precision, Recall
17	[Liu et al. 2025b]	Others	GRU	Dynamic, Heterogeneous	Edge	Others	Yes	Yes	Network, System, Others	LANL; CERT r6.2	Precision, ROC, Recall
18	[Guan et al. 2025]	GCN	LSTM	Dynamic, Heterogeneous	Edge	GAN, SMOTE	Yes	Yes	Network, System	UNSW, etc.	F1, ROC
19	[Xiao et al. 2025]	GAT	Time-aware Att.	Dynamic, Heterogeneous	Node	Focal Loss	No	Yes	Network, System, Others	CERT r4.2	F1, ROC
20	[Liu et al. 2025a]	Heterogeneous GNN	None	Static, Heterogeneous	Node	None	No	Yes	Network, System, Others	CERT r4.2	ROC, Recall
21	[Han et al. 2026]	GATv2	GRU	Dynamic, Heterogeneous	Node	Focal Loss	No	Yes	System	BGL, HDFS, Thunderbird	F1, ROC, Recall
22	[He et al. 2026]	Others	None	Static, Heterogeneous	Node	None	No	No	System, Others	BGL, HDFS, Thunderbird	F1, PR-AUC, Precision, Recall

Figure 1 presents the study selection workflow adopted in the SLM. The workflow follows a PRISMA-inspired structure adapted for systematic mapping studies. The selection process reduced the initial set of 485 studies to a final corpus of 22 high-quality primary studies.

Figure 1. Study Selection Workflow of the SLM

Table 3 presents a synthesis of the 22 primary studies selected in the systematic mapping, organized chronologically and analyzed according to different technical dimensions relevant to graph-based insider threat detection. The table consolidates information related to graph architectures, temporal components, graph representations, detection levels, imbalance mitigation strategies, synthetic data generation approaches, datasets, and evaluation metrics adopted in the experimental validation of the models. The literature demonstrates a progressive evolution toward more expressive and sophisticated architectures. Recent studies show a predominance of GNN-based approaches, frequently integrated with attention mechanisms, heterogeneous graph representations, and temporal components such as LSTMs and sequential models. Additionally, an increasing adoption of imbalance mitigation strategies can be observed, including synthetic data generation techniques based on GANs, especially in scenarios involving rare and highly asymmetric events. The results also reveal a strong dependence on well-established cybersecurity datasets, such as CERT, LANL, and BGL, reinforcing the importance of these benchmarks for experimental validation in insider threat detection research.

This synthesis enables the identification of important research trends, particularly the growth of hybrid spatiotemporal models and the increasing adoption of dynamic and heterogeneous graph representations. At the same time, the analysis also highlights important research gaps related to evaluation in highly imbalanced scenarios, the limited

adoption of metrics specifically designed for rare-event detection, and the relatively low exploration of graph-level relational reasoning approaches.

Figure 2. Distribution of the primary studies selected in the SLM according to digital libraries and publication year.

Figure 3. Distribution of evaluation metrics and detection levels in the selected primary studies.

Figure 4. Percentage distribution of graph representations adopted in the selected primary studies.

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